

GUIDELINES FOR OPERATIONALISING THE DATA

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Executive summary

Among the goals of the *Developing Inclusive & Sustainable Creative Economies* (DISCE) project, is the need to collect quantitative data and improve the state of the art of the creative economy and creative and cultural industries (CCIs) from a statistical viewpoint. As highlighted in the “Measuring creative economies: existing models & the DISCE approach” (see the previous report), there is no clear consensus about the definition of creative economy itself. However, this report aims to investigate the most important variables and indices to define CCIs.

In the first part of the project, WP2 is devoted in gathering data at different levels of analysis: country, regional (NUTS2), province (NUTS3) and city. This strategy allows both academics and policy makers to have a consistent overview of all the available data related to several aspects of CCIs, such as: cultural venues and facilities, cultural participation and attractiveness, creative and knowledge-based jobs, and so forth. Moreover, this phase covers not only different characteristics of CCIs, but also information about their components (i.e. supply, culture consumption, tourism, education) and socio-economic and institutional variables. These latter have been included to provide a detailed description of the CCIs contexts (UNESCO, 2019).

In the second part, following the *Handbook on constructing composite index manual* (OECD, 2008), several composite indexes on creative and cultural industries (CCC Index) will be developed through an in depth analysis of variables identified during the first phase. The representativeness of these indicators will be then tested across the project, and in particular after the analyses of single case studies.

The third part is related to firm-level data. After the identification of the NACE2 codes of CCIs, financial and structural information on firms belonging to these sectors are extracted from the Amadeus – Bureau van Dijk databases. These data include also the geographical localisation of firms, i.e. the latitude and longitude. Therefore, it is possible to represent the geographical distribution of these firms through maps and network-analysis, and better investigate the agglomeration forces which push these companies to settle in the same areas or regions. Adding the geographical aspects will help to draw a complete picture of the CCIs from different perspectives.

The time span of the quantitative data is from 2000 to 2018 and it covers all the CCIs in EU-28 countries.

Different methods to measure CCIs

According to the CCIs literature, there are very different aspects to consider when measuring these industries (Ortega-Villa & Ley-Garcia, 2018). The first issue concerns the direction of analysis: from one side it could be demand-driven, when the focus is the impact of cultural industries on economic growth; on the other side is product-driven when it considers the factors (geographical, institutional, social) that affect the CCIs development (Potts, 2011; Towse, 2011; UNESCO, 2009). This division between demand and supply side is challenged throughout the DISCE case study framework and the WP5 literature review, supporting a more 'ecological' approach (Wilson, 2020). However, for the purposes of this report to provide an overview of the existing data and existing approaches, the production and consumption classifications are used as valid definitions of the phenomenon.

Regarding the output side, among the most common variables are employment growth rate and value added or GDP. Cerisola (2018) and Piergiovanni et al. (2012) have studied the effects of different creative components on employment and value added for Italian provinces. Both studies show that there exists a positive relation between province growth and the presence of CCIs. Crociata et al. (2015) investigate the spatial evolution of the creative workforce and the economic growth associated to CCIs for several regions in Europe in the pre-crisis period. Their findings support the idea that some regions attract and maintain higher percentages of creative employees, following a clear spatial pattern across Europe. The empirical analysis reveals that the surrounding environment plays an important role when looking at the development and growth of CCIs.

Thus, do creative industries drive economic growth, or is the relationship the other way around? The study by Marco-Serrano et al. (2014), tries to solve this question by analysing regional European data for ten years between 1999 and 2008. In their study, they proxy economic growth through regional income generation and the contribution of CCIs is represented by the number of employees in those industries. Their findings reveal that the relationship exists in both ways, as CCIs attract skilled workforce and qualified human capital that in turn positively affect the economic growth of the European regions (Marco-Serrano et al., 2014).

Another aspect that deserves attention due to the aim of the DISCE project is the sustainability and tolerance related to the CCIs framework (KEA & PPMI, 2019). Boschma and Fritsch (2009) study the regional distribution of the creative employees for seven European countries, with respect to tolerance and openness behaviours. Their findings support the relation between these two concepts, in particular for areas characterised by high-

skilled workforce, which contributes to higher regional growth rates and higher degrees of tolerance. In the same vein, Bagwell (2008) develops a case study of six jewellery clusters in the City Fringe area of London to better understand local economic development and social inclusion aspects. In this area, the prevalence of ethnic minority groups is a driver for inclusivity purposes of creative industries, along with the development of qualified human capital and public support.

Besides human capital (Marrocu & Paci, 2012) and market structures (Comunian, Chapain, & Clifton, 2010), it is interesting to investigate which are the factors, that might play a role in the creation of CCIs. Taking the local and regional perspective as the unit of analysis, Chapain and Comunian (2010) highlight four categories that affect the development of CCIs in two cities/regions in UK: personal dimension, operational sphere, networking aspects and regional infrastructures. The assets of these two areas, in particular the size and infrastructures play a fundamental part in attracting creative firms. The role of network has been stressed also by Drda-Kühn and Wiegand (2010) for what concerns small towns in rural areas in Germany. With respect to Chapain and Comunian (2010), where the unit of analysis was influenced by the power of the large metropolitan city of London, the case of Altenkirchen shows an environment where CCIs are still at their preliminary stages. Here, the enabling factors are represented by the strong presence of networks which connect public administration, tourism industry, business communities and local cultural community. The importance of network and cluster initiatives is supported by the study conducted in Italy and Spain by Lazzarotti et al. (2012). The authors find similar patterns as in the UK for Spain, where cultural industries are located close to big cities, while in Italy they are dispersed along the territory. These results are explained through the importance of urbanization economies (Lorenzen & Frederiksen, 2008), which are denser in Spain rather than in Italy.

As reported in previous studies, there is no clear consensus on which is the most appropriate way to measure CCIs and which is the representative unit of analysis (Markusen, 2013). The next section reports some of the variables, at different unit-level, that mainly describe CCIs from a quantitative viewpoint.

Guidelines for operationalising the data

Data collection process

The DISCE project is seeking to improve and enhance the growth, inclusivity and sustainability of the CCIs across EU. In doing so, it is essential to develop a more comprehensive and systematic understanding of CCIs (KEA, 2018). A key step towards this direction consists of providing robust evidence about CCIs' definitions and measurement by using available statistical information in relation to the literature presented in the previous section.

According to the level of analysis, different sources were exploited to collect information on CCIs. At the Country level: The World Bank, UNESCO, the United Nations Development Programme (UNPD), European Commission and EUROSTAT, UNCTAD, OECD, The Quality of Government Institute (University of Gothenburg), the International Council of Museums (ICOM) and the World Economic Forum were the main data sources. Some of them, like OECD and EUROSTAT, present data at regional (NUTS2) and province (NUTS3) level, that are merged with information from the National Statistic Offices to have finer grain observations. Moreover, National Statistic Offices is an interesting source for what concerns city level data. Some of these big cities (Berlin, Paris, Florence, Barcelona, Budapest to cite some of them) are the focus of a recent report by the European Commission (2019), where variables on creative and cultural cities are accompanied by other indicators of inclusivity and tolerance at city level.

Tables on data description and summary statistics are reported in the Appendix of WP3.

The procedure to collect all the aforementioned data comprehends four different steps:

1. Mapping information. The first step consisted of mapping all the available sources of quantitative data concerning CCIs at both national and local level across European countries, through web scraping and in-depth report analysis.

2. Collecting quantitative data. The second step consists of collecting the statistical data and indicators for CCI's according to the classification defined by European Commission. The information gathered covers the different sectors of CCI's and its components (i.e. supply, culture consumption, tourism, education). Moreover, socio-economic and institutional variables have been gathered in order to provide a detailed description of the contexts where CCI's are developing. Data has been collected and systematised in a database including regions names and NUTS codes as well as all the variables of interest and their metadata.
3. Adding other variables. A third step consisted of adding to this first data collection strictly focusing on CCI's other dimensions that are currently considered as related to them and those that we would like to link to CCI's in the next future, e.g. Well-being Index (OECD), Regional Innovation Scoreboard (European Commission) and EU Social Progress Index (European Commission).
4. Sharing information. A fourth step consisted of sharing the knowledge regarding the geographies of NUTS 2 and NUTS 3 regions as well as the quantitative data collected with all the project partners in order to create a first common understanding concerning our contextual data.

In particular, during the first step WP2 has collaborated with other WPs in the identification of case study locations. Via the case studies, the semi-structured interviews and workshops will give provide additional information to inform the development of new understandings of the creative economy, including aspects / variables that are not currently included within existing 'CCI's' data sets. These may relate, for example, to key aspects of 'inclusivity', 'sustainability' and 'growth' - understood in new ways. The data from each case study location will be analysed and compared with other regions both in the same country, and across countries.

The composite index: general framework

A recently released report by UNESCO (2019) presents seven possible thematic indicators that might quantitatively describe the CCIs:

1. *expenditure on heritage*: this index expresses the ration between the sum of public and private expenditure over population; it proxies for the total expenditure on all cultural and natural heritage.
2. *culture in GDP*: it represents the total amount of GDP expenditure in CCIs over the national GDP to have an overview of the overall contribution of the culture sector to the economy in a given territory.
3. *cultural employment*: is the ratio between population employed in the creative sector over the total employed people to understand how much CCIs are helpful in increasing the overall employment.
4. *cultural business*: this indicator highlights the conditions to develop cultural business; it is a trend indicator as far as it reports a time series of the number of cultural establishments at time 't' with respect to time t-1.
5. *household expenditure*: this indicator measures the share of household expenditure for cultural activities and it represents how much people are willing to spend in cultural activities and related goods and services.
6. *multilingual education*: this index shows the number of instructional hours dedicated to official/national languages with respect to regional or local languages.
7. *culture for social cohesion*: this is a composite indicator that groups tolerance, trust and gender quality data, and proxies for the degree of inter-cultural understanding and personal acceptance.

While the first five indicators are strictly related to 'creative' and 'cultural' aspects (narrowly defined), the last two are devoted to measure inclusivity and sustainability. In particular, *multilingual education* gives some indication of the level of multilingualism promotion during the schooling years and of intercultural dialogue; and *the culture for social cohesion* indicator provides a measure of possible opportunity gaps between sexual gender or racial disparities (UNESCO, 2019).

These thematic indicators give a general overview of the main variables related to the CCIs. Apart from this general indicator, there are other several indicators at country level such as: Czech Creative Index (CZCI) (Kloudová & Stehlíková, 2010), the Composite Index of the Creative Economy (CICE) (Bowen, Moesen, & Sleuwaegen, 2008), European Creativity Index (ECI) (KEA, 2009) to cite some of them (for an extensive review of the other indicators see Correia and da Silva Costa (2014)).

However, among the aims of the DISCE project is to assemble a composite Cultural Development Index. (For further discussion of how the WP5 team is conceptualizing this index, see the WP5 literature review).

Guidelines for developing a composite index are provided in the *Handbook on constructing composite index* manual (OECD, 2008). There are three main steps to follow:

1. **Theoretical framework:** during this phase, theoretical and empirical contributions (reports, academic papers, business studies) provide the basis for the selection and combination of variables into a meaningful composite indicator under a fitness-for-purpose principle.
2. **Data selection:** is based on the analytical soundness, measurability, country coverage, and relevance of the indicators to the phenomenon being measured. Data source and level of analysis could be different. If data are not available or scarce, they can be approximated with the closest proxy variables.
3. **Data analysis:** this is the most important part and it is divided in four sub-phases. It starts with a multivariate analysis, via principle component (PCA) or cluster analysis (CA), to study the overall structure of the dataset. Through PCA or CA are highlighted the most suitable variables and the respective weights. As far as not all the variables are equal, the second phase is devoted to the normalisation of the variables via ranking, standardisation, min-max scaling to render all the variables comparable. The third step consists in the weighting and aggregation of variables in line with the theoretical framework proposed at Step.1. Finally, to be sure that the composite indicator is robust and representative, uncertainty and sensitivity analysis are performed in terms of e.g., the mechanism for including or excluding an indicator, the normalisation scheme, the imputation of missing data, the choice of weights, the aggregation method.

An example of a composite indicator is the Global Creativity Index (GCI) (Florida, Mellander, & King, 2015), based on the 3Ts paradigm of economic development (Florida, 2002). The GCI is a broad-based measure for advanced economic growth and sustainable prosperity, and each T represents: (i.) technology, a standard measure of R&D effort, proxied by the share of GDP devoted to R&D, and the standard measure of innovation, based on patents; (ii.) talent (or human capital), that comprehends educational and occupational measures of talent; and (iii.) tolerance, that accounts for the openness to ethnic and religious minorities and to gay and lesbian people.

Despite the very interesting framework and usefulness of this indicator, the final output is a composite index at country level, which has some pitfall when is statistically tested against urban income and job growth (Crocicci et al., 2015; Hoyman & Faricy, 2009).

What we intend to develop through the DISCE project is a more sophisticated index, at regional or province level, to have a finer grain analysis on how CCIs are distributed and affect local economies. In doing so, we are also – crucially – reconceptualising what the ‘creative economy’ is, and how key terms including inclusivity, sustainability and growth need to be understood. (For further discussion of this, see the Case Study Framework document, and the WP5 literature review.)

Firm level analysis

The last phase of operationalising the data is devoted to collect data at firm level. In particular, during this phase National Statistical Offices and Bureau van Dijk databases will be exploited to collect financial and structural information about cultural and creative companies. Georeferenced data will be extracted to map the distribution of firms across Europe.

The final database comprehends all the firms in Europe from 2009 to 2016, belonging to the Nace Rev. 2 (EUROSTAT, 2008) codes following the Guide to Eurostat culture statistics (EUROSTAT, 2018) reported in Table 1.

Tab.1: Nace Rev. 2 codes for CCIs.

Code	Description	Code	Description
18.11	Printing of newspaper	71.11	Architectural activities
18.12	Other printing	71.12	Engineering activities and related consultancy
18.13	Pre-press and pre-media services	72.11	Research and experimental development in biotechnology
18.14	Binding and related services	72.19	Other research and exp. development on natural sciences and engineering
18.2	Reproduction of recorded media	72.2	Research and exp. development on social sciences and humanities
58.11	Book publishing	73.11	Advertising agencies
58.13	Publishing of newspapers	73.12	Media representation
58.14	Publishing of journals and periodicals	74.1	Specialised design activities
58.21	Publishing of computer games	74.2	Photographic activities
58.29	Other software publishing	90.01	Performing arts
59.11	Motion picture, video and television programme production activities	90.03	Artistic creation
59.2	Sound recording and music publishing	91.01	Library and archives activities

60.1	Radio broadcasting	91.02	Museum activities
60.2	Television programming and broadcasting	91.03	Operation of historical sites and buildings and similar visitor attractions
62.01	Computer programming activities	91.04	Botanical and zoological gardens and nature reserves activities
62.09	Other information technology and computer service activities	93.21	Activities of amusement parks and theme parks

Having these additional firm-level data merged with local-level data (for example the Quality of Government and infrastructures), the accessibility to cultural venues and the degree of inclusivity and sustainability, will ensure a very in-depth analysis of the creative and cultural economy at the current stage of development.

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